
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article focuses on the priority directions in the development of the new Uzbekistan, and presents the constitutional foundations for strengthening the sovereignty and stability of the country. Dramatic changes in domestic and foreign policy are outlined. Particular attention is paid to strengthening national values based on interests and human rights.

Key words: statehood, stability, constitutional norms, youth policy, strategy «Uzbekistan-2023».

ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ СТРАТЕГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация: В статье акцентируется внимание на приоритетные направления в развитии нового Узбекистана, представлены конституционные основы укрепления суверенитета и стабильности страны. Обозначены кардинальные изменения во внутренней и внешней политике. Особое внимание уделено укреплению национальных ценностей, основанных на интересах и правах человека.

Ключевые слова: государственность, стабильность, конституционные нормы, молодежная политика, стратегия «Узбекистан-2023».

INTRODUCTION.

Gaining independence is the story not only of statehood, but also of the people, the destinies of people, and the future of the country. That is why sovereignty is the most important value for any state. For citizens, peaceful life and stability in society represent the main achievements that independence brings.

Peace and stability reigning in our country today, interethnic harmony, an atmosphere of kindness and mercy, constant care for people in need of help and attention - all this noble work has become an integral part of state policy. Peace and tranquility, civil harmony, religious tolerance, equal participation of representatives of different cultures in the life of society are the distinctive features of the New Uzbekistan, the experience of which is valuable in strengthening and encouraging interreligious and intercultural dialogue.

LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY.

The study of the current state of the strategy of the new Uzbekistan in priority areas indicates the determination of the regulatory framework that confirms the relevance and significance of the problem. In this:

1. Article 1 of the Constitution in the new edition states: Uzbekistan is a sovereign, democratic, legal, social and secular state with a republican form of government [1].

2. As stated in Article 2, the state expresses the will of the people and serves their interests. State bodies and officials are responsible to society and citizens. In turn, Article 8 states: the people of Uzbekistan are citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality [2].

3. Reforms in the country are carried out under the motto «Only united - we are one people, only together - we are a strong country!» [3].

In 2024, the country will celebrate its 33rd anniversary of independence. As part of the celebration of this significant date, numerous events were organized locally aimed at strengthening national unity, promoting the cultural heritage and achievements of Uzbekistan. Literary and artistic evenings, national cinema days, national celebrations, sporting events, gastronomic festivals, authoritative international conferences and symposiums, scientific achievements in various fields of activity, enthusiasm in entrepreneurship and the business environment and much more are the result of the fruitful embodiment of life-affirming potential countries in all areas.

As noted in the Presidential Decree «On the preparation and celebration of the thirty-third anniversary of the state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated July 18, 2024: «It is thanks to independence that our country has become a sovereign, democratic, legal, social and secular state, a full-fledged subject of international law. The world has come to know and recognize us anew. Relations of friendship and cooperation with various states and peoples are expanding, and the authority of our Motherland in the international arena is growing» [4].

In his speech, dedicated to the independence of Uzbekistan, the head of state Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted the importance of large-scale democratic reforms carried out in the country in recent years. It was emphasized «a deep awareness of the

happiness, honor and enormous responsibility of being an independent state open to the world, occupying a worthy place in the family of free nations, achieving a modern level of development»⁶.

Radical changes in domestic and foreign policy aimed at ensuring national interests, the practical results achieved are receiving recognition and support from the international community.

Since the day Uzbekistan gained independence, there have been enormous changes in all spheres of life in the country. Economic growth, social stability and political independence - all this became possible thanks to the efforts of the people.

Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shakhrisabz, Termez and Kokand are cities known far beyond the borders of Uzbekistan as architectural centers of art, culture and science. Palaces, mausoleums, mosques and minarets erected on this land have taken their place in the annals of world history. In the Middle Ages, Uzbekistan was the heart of the Great Silk Road, which contributed to the development of unique architectural projects.

The emphasis on the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan increases the importance of comparative analysis as a method of obtaining broad information on the creative work being carried out. In this regard, it is worth noting the launch of large industrial production facilities, numerous small business and private entrepreneurship facilities. Residential buildings, roads and bridges, infrastructure, educational, scientific, health, cultural and sports facilities are being built. Wide roads, recreation areas, educational institutions from the outskirts of Karakalpakstan to remote villages of the Fergana Valley are pleasing to the eye. In addition, new overground stations of the Tashkent metro are being put into operation. We are witnessing large-scale reforms, economic growth in all areas, which reflects the aspirations of the people, dreams and intentions.

The historicism method helps to study the conditions for implementing measures aimed at asserting the principles of independence and national values at the local level. Representatives of the youth environment take an active part in various traditional competitions such as «Image of the Motherland through the Eyes of an Artist», «Live in the Name of the Motherland!», «The Greatest, the Dearest», which are aimed at strengthening patriotism, cultural heritage and national pride in the younger generation.

In recent years, the republic has achieved high rates of economic growth and made significant steps in the field of sustainable development. The introduction of modern technologies and diversification of the economy are among the main strategies of the state, which ensures the creation of new jobs and improvement of the

⁶ Там же.

population's life. Along with this, Uzbekistan has become one of the key players in the region in the field of transport and energy.

An important part of the reforms is also the development of the law enforcement system, strengthening the rights of citizens and the fight against corruption. Such steps allow our people to participate more actively in decision-making and shaping their destiny.

The observation method can be used to identify current trends aimed at increasing care for young people. In this regard, 2024 has been declared the Year of Support for Youth and Business, thus denoting the country's desire to strengthen the role of the younger generation in socio-economic development and support for entrepreneurship. This includes the creation of special funds to finance innovative projects of young people, the development of programs to stimulate business entities and the provision of microloans. The importance of the active participation of young people in the process of modernizing society through the development of their scientific potential and obtaining a decent education is also enshrined in the Strategy «Uzbekistan – 2030». The main vector here is the implementation of measures to create every citizen with all the opportunities to develop their potential, raise a healthy, educated and spiritually developed generation, form a strong economy that has become an important link in global production, as well as guarantee justice, the rule of law, security and stability.

RESULTS.

Why does Uzbekistan pay so much attention to youth? Young people have always been a source of innovation and pioneering. They have the courage and energy that is necessary for business and development in the spheres of economy and politics, as well as in education and culture. The state strives to create conditions conducive to the development of young men and women, ensuring the implementation of the idea of «New Uzbekistan - the third Renaissance» under the motto «Youth - creators of the New Uzbekistan».

Our country continues to improve its efforts to develop strategic plans aimed at supporting youth and developing entrepreneurship. This year, the main focus is on creating additional opportunities for the younger generation with an emphasis on unlocking their potential. Thus, it is planned to double the number of young people sent through the El-Yurt Umidi Foundation to prestigious foreign universities in order to support free-thinking and creative youth. Half of them will be sent to study technical and exact sciences, IT.

In the context of the Strategy «Uzbekistan – 2030», attention has also been increased to supporting entrepreneurship and business development. Last year, 236 thousand young people were employed in each mahalla on the basis of the Youth Employment Program. The system of higher and vocational education covers 189

thousand school graduates. According to the planned priority tasks, this year in each region in the system of ministries and departments a completely new approach to working with young people is being introduced, the types of assistance provided on the recommendation of a youth leader are being transformed. Particular attention is paid to training in modern professions.

DISCUSSION.

The Five Initiatives Olympiad project covers 12 million young people. 623 sports grounds have been built in mahallas for young men and women who have become winners and prize winners of the project. Also, in 2023, the types of assistance provided through the Youth Notebook system have increased to 30.

The priority task of the state is to create conditions for a free, comfortable and prosperous life for women, which is enshrined in the Strategy «Uzbekistan – 2030». Within the framework of the document, large-scale measures are being implemented aimed at increasing the political, social and economic activity of compatriots, protecting motherhood and childhood, affirming gender equality, and ensuring their rights and interests.

In addition, Uzbekistan has adopted regulations guaranteeing women equal pay with men for work of equal value. Restrictions on the employment of women in certain industries have been lifted.

It is important to note that the country has introduced regulations protecting women from domestic violence. In April 2023, amendments were made to the Criminal Code and the Code of Administrative Responsibility aimed at combating domestic violence, including physical, psychological and economic violence. Criminal liability has been established for these types of crimes. The growing level of political and legal culture of women, their social activity can be observed at all levels of state and public administration, in all spheres of life of our society [5].

Speaking at a festive event on the occasion of March 8, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that within the framework of the State Program 2024, five thousand women in need of complex surgeries and who find themselves in a difficult life situation will undergo treatment at the expense of the State Budget and international financial institutions. At the same time, one million pregnant women and 1.5 million nursing mothers were provided with iodine preparations free of charge, about six million women of reproductive age - with iron preparations and folic acid. In addition, four thousand compatriots who found themselves in a difficult life situation were provided with assistance in housing.

Since March 2024, the Girls Academy platform has been launched to teach young women and girls entrepreneurship, marketing and graphic design. The project also organizes various competitions, training camps and internships.

Thanks to the great attention and specific measures taken by the head of state to develop the family and implement effective policies in this direction, the material situation and quality of life of families are consistently improving, and their spiritual and moral state is strengthening.

CONCLUSION.

The 33rd anniversary of independence is an important milestone in the history of our country. During this period, Uzbekistan has overcome many difficulties and achieved significant success in its development. At the same time, fast-paced times require everyone to set ever higher goals. Today, one of the main tasks is aimed at achieving an independent state and a free society, which will be created by the strength and potential of our people. This is a high milestone, worthy of tireless work. This is a bright, glorious goal, to which it is worth dedicating one's life. Only by uniting, mobilizing all knowledge, experience, strength and energy, these goals of a wonderful future - New Uzbekistan - will definitely be achieved.

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